

DETERMINING THE INTER-PLY AND INTRA-PLY VISCOSITIES OF UNI-AXIAL THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY THE ROLLER BEND METHOD

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SUMMARY: As high-speed manufacturing technology for forming continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTs) has developed, the need to reliably characterise the thermo-rheological material properties of CFRTs has increased. This paper investigates the primary deformation mechanism of viscous shear and considers the development of an experimental method to determine the inter-ply and the intra-ply shear properties of uni-directional laminates. By simply melting the strips and pulling them through a series of rollers, the steady state drawing forces are measured and related to the material's longitudinal viscosity. The advantage of using this method lies in its ease of execution. The results show that, while the inter-ply shear viscosity of PLYTRON is slightly lower than the intra-ply shear viscosity, it is much higher than that reported elsewhere. The polymer also displays a typical shear thinning behaviour. The *roller bend technique* can be used to characterise the shear properties of many other thermoplastic composites.

KEYWORDS: inter-ply shear viscosity, thermoplastic composite sheets, continuous fibres

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRT) materials have become increasingly popular in recent years due to the relative ease with which they can be molded into components. By simply melting the matrix polymer and applying moderate forces, complex geometries can be formed. In this molten state the matrix behaves like a viscous liquid and the fibres, which retain their elasticity, introduce a high degree of anisotropy into the material. To predict the physical response of these materials in a real forming situation, it is necessary to firstly understand the way in which they deform and secondly to determine their relevant material properties. Thus it is important to consider the hierarchy of flow mechanisms described by Cogswell and Leach [1]; resin percolation, transverse squeeze flow, inter-ply shear and intra-ply shear. These four flow mechanisms pertain to CFRT sheets with uni-directional plies and they are commonly present in combination, depending on the forming operation. Resin percolation and transverse squeeze flow, are typically associated with consolidation and welding processes, so they are not the main focus of this paper. However, inter-ply and intra-ply shear, are absolutely essential for shaping processes which induce

single and double curvature in a sheet. To form parts with single curvature the plies must shear through their thicknesses or slide over one another in the resin rich layers between the plies. When double curvature is required, intra-ply shear also takes place, that is, shear along the fibres within the plane of the sheet. In order to progress towards analytical/numerical forming solutions, which accurately reflect real moulding processes, both these mechanisms require investigation.

To quantify the viscous material properties of CFRTs, a number of authors have suggested various types of experimental methods; the ply pull-out test [2], the torsional rheometry test [3], the picture frame test [4] and the vee-bend test [5]. These techniques have various problems associated with them. The ply pull-out test often leads to gross fibre bundle movement during testing which alters the material behaviour and the transverse movement of the plies cannot be easily constrained. The torsional rheometry test is really only suited to infinitesimal deformations and the longitudinal shear response cannot be separated from the transverse shear response, without making prior assumptions about the material's constitutive behaviour. The picture frame test suffers from a similar problem. Furthermore, the flow mechanism is complicated by inducing squeeze flow within the plane of the sheet. A vee-bend test provides a much better method for determining the inter-ply shear properties of CFRT laminates, but it is not suitable for measuring the intra-ply shear properties and much data reduction is required to calculate the viscosity of the material from the non-linear load response curves.

This paper examines a new method for measuring the shear properties of CFRTs. *The roller bend technique* is experimentally simpler than any previously suggested methods, induces finite strains at realistic strain rates and specifically isolates the shear response of the material. Consider the schematic diagram of the experimental set-up shown in Figure 1. An initially straight laminate, with its fibres aligned along its length, is forced to shear through its thickness by bending around three rollers. In this case, a plane strain forming condition is enforced by circular side plates, indicated by dotted circles in Figure 1. The deformation is therefore entirely kinematically specified in the bend region. As the strip is pulled upwards it experiences a positive-negative-positive shear sequence, so that it exits the final roll as a flat sheet. The strip is pulled through the rollers until a steady state is reached, and for each forming speed the measured drawing force can be directly related to the steady state viscosity of the material. In addition, by turning the specimen 90° in the test apparatus, either the intra-ply or inter-ply material properties can be readily measured. This approach could be adopted as a standard technique to measure and compare the viscous properties of various thermoplastic composite laminates in their molten states. While this paper investigates PLYTRON test specimens, the objective is not to provide an exhaustive study of the shear properties of PLYTRON, but rather to demonstrate the principle of the *roller bend technique*.

THEORY

The analytical model presented in this section yields a mathematical description of the effects of the forming speed and the roller/strip geometry on the steady state drawing forces. The theory pertains to an idealised material model, which accounts for the fluid nature of the molten polymer and the high elongational stiffness of the fibres, by treating the composite like an incompressible viscous continuum containing thin homogeneously distributed inextensible cords [6].

Fig. 1: A diagram of the roller bend test concept

Constraints and Kinematics

In the continuum considered here the fibres all lie in parallel surfaces in the plane of deformation and each fibre path is characterised by a field of unit tangent vectors, \mathbf{a} , as shown in Figure 2. The components of \mathbf{a} are denoted a_i . During the deformation the fibres are convected with the continuum, so that the same material particles lie on the same fibre at any given time. The orthogonal trajectories to the \mathbf{a} -lines are characterised by a field of unit normal vectors, \mathbf{n} . The components of \mathbf{n} are denoted n_i . The \mathbf{n} -lines are not material curves in general, because the particles lying on an \mathbf{n} -line before deformation will not necessarily lie on the same \mathbf{n} -line after deformation. We now consider the kinematic constraints imposed on this idealised material. The incompressibility and fibre inextensibility conditions are respectively expressed by

$$\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_i} = d_{ii} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad a_i a_j \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} = a_i a_j d_{ij} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2: An idealised sheet wrapped around a roller.

where x refers to the spatial coordinates of the velocity vector, \mathbf{v} , and d_{ij} is the rate of deformation tensor defined by

$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (2)$$

The rate of change of \mathbf{a} is given by

$$\dot{a}_i = a_k \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_k} \quad (3)$$

For a detailed derivation of these equations the reader is referred to Rogers and O'Neill [7]. Consider the deformation of a flat sheet wrapped around a single roller in Figure 2. Two side plates, not illustrated in the diagram, are positioned on either side of the large central roller to prevent the laminate from spreading normal to the plane.

Pipkin and Rogers [8] have derived the governing equations for plane strain deformations of incompressible, inextensible materials and two significant results follow from their work: (a) the initially straight fibres remain in parallel surfaces, so the normal lines main straight and (b) the thickness of the sheet does not change during forming. These two requirements permit only simple shear deformations along the fibres. The amount of shear in the continuum is measured by the change in angle between two adjacent fibres. As there is no deformation up to the normal line BG in Figure 2, the shear strain along any normal line in the fan region BCFG is equal to the fibre angle, ϕ , and the shear rate is equal to the rate of rotation of a normal line, $\dot{\phi}$.

Stress in a Constrained Material

The total stress in a constrained material can be thought of as the sum of a reaction stress, r_{ij} , and an extra stress, S_{ij} .

$$\sigma_{ij} = r_{ij} + S_{ij} = -p(\delta_{ij} - a_i a_j) + T a_i a_j + S_{ij} \quad (4)$$

where S_{ij} satisfies the constraints $a_i a_j S_{ij} = 0$ and $n_i n_j S_{ij} = 0$. In other words, S_{ij} has no normal stress component on surface elements normal to the \mathbf{a} direction or the \mathbf{n} direction. The reaction stress does no work in a deformation and the reactions p and T arise as a result of the incompressibility and fibre inextensibility constraints respectively. T is the total tension on elements normal to the fibre direction and p represents the total pressure on elements normal to the \mathbf{n} direction. These scalar terms must be determined by solving the equilibrium equations, whereas the deviatoric stress tensor, S_{ij} , needs to be specified by an appropriate constitutive relationship. If the material has reflectional symmetry in the x_3 plane and the deformation is homogeneous, under plane strain conditions the only non-zero components of σ_{ij} are

$$\sigma_{ij} = -p(\delta_{ij} - a_i a_j) + T a_i a_j + S(a_i n_j + a_j n_i) + S_{33} k_i k_j \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{k} is the vector normal to the plane of deformation.

Constitutive Equation

In the present analysis, the deformation of an incompressible fluid reinforced with a single family of inextensible fibres in the (x_1, x_2) plane is considered. According to Rogers [9], the constitutive relationship for a viscous fluid subjected to these two constraints is given by

$$S_{ij} = 2\mu_T d_{ij} + 2(\mu_L - \mu_T)(a_i a_k d_{kj} + a_j a_k d_{ki}) \quad (6)$$

where μ_L and μ_T are the respective viscosities of the continuum along and transverse to the fibres. In a plane strain deformation, $v_3 = d_{33} = 0$, so that, $\sigma_{33} = -p$. Hence, a stress must be applied normal to the plane of deformation to maintain the plane strain condition. Using equations (5) and (6) it is readily shown that

$$S = a_i n_j \sigma_{ij} = a_i n_j S_{ij} = 2\mu_L a_i n_j d_{ij} = \mu_L \dot{\phi} \quad (7)$$

where S is the shear stress associated with simple shear along the fibre direction. For a viscous fluid model, S depends only on the shear rate. In this particular example the only material property which can be determined in the constitutive equation is the longitudinal shear viscosity, μ_L . If a shear thinning fluid material model is chosen, instead of a linear viscous fluid model, then a power law expression for the apparent viscosity, μ_L , as a function of the shear rate can be introduced, so that

$$\mu_L = \frac{S}{\dot{\phi}} = m_L \dot{\phi}^{n-1} \quad (8)$$

where m_L is the pseudo longitudinal shear thinning viscosity and n is the consistency index. By including fibre layers in the laminate which are not aligned with the longitudinal direction, the transverse shear viscosity may also be determined [5]. So a similar expression could be written for μ_T in terms of m_T and n . It is likely that n depends only on the shear thinning behaviour of the matrix polymer and is unaffected by the anisotropy in the composite, although it could be a function of the fibre volume fraction. When $n=1$ the fluid becomes Newtonian.

Stress Equilibrium

Consider the equilibrium of the force resultants acting on an elementary cross section of the deformed plate shown in Figure 3. When the only boundary traction is the pressure exerted on the inner surface, it is a simple matter to deduce that

$$\frac{\partial T^*}{\partial \phi} - S^* = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad T^* + \frac{\partial S^*}{\partial \phi} = r_0 p_0 \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3: Stress Equilibrium in a Polar Coordinate System

The force resultants, S^* and T^* , are the resultant shear and tensile forces per unit length in the \mathbf{k} direction acting across a normal line $\phi = \text{constant}$.

$$S^* = \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} S dr \quad \text{and} \quad (10)$$

$$T^* = \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} T dr$$

Velocity Field Kinematics

If we now consider the velocity field equations for plane strain deformations and resolve the 2-D velocity vectors along the \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{n} directions, two important equations may be obtained. In a polar coordinate system, the incompressibility and inextensibility equations (1) become

$$\frac{\partial v_n}{\partial r} + v_a \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial v_a}{\partial \phi} - v_n = 0 \quad (11)$$

These two equations (Geiringer's equations) have been presented in their more general form by Spencer[6], along with the following equation for the shear rate, which is derived from (3)

$$\dot{\phi} = \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial v_n}{\partial \phi} + v_a \right) \quad (12)$$

Using equations (7)-(12), the shear stress, the fibre tension and the surface pressure can be determined for the entire sheet, when the kinematics of the deformation are prescribed as a continuous function of time. In this theoretical model the requirement that the normal lines remain straight during forming means that $\partial \phi / \partial r = 0$; so equation (11) yields $v_n = f(\phi)$.

An Admissible Stress Solution

In the following stress analysis, the boundary conditions are fixed in time and space and the kinematic model leads to a statically admissible stress solution. In order to determine the stress state in the sheet, we again refer to the geometry in Figure 2. In regions ABGH and CDEF the strip is straight and the shear rate is zero. Therefore $S^* = 0$ in these two regions. In the fan region BCFG, $v_n = 0$ and $v_a = \text{const} = V$, by the second equation (11), so the resultant shear force is derived from equations (7), (8), (10) and (12).

$$S^* = \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} \mu_L \dot{\phi} dr = \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} m_L \dot{\phi}^n dr = \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} m_L \left(\frac{V}{r} \right)^n dr = \frac{m_L V^n}{1-n} \left[\frac{1}{(r_0+h)^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{r_0^{n-1}} \right] \quad (13)$$

Consequently S^* is positive in the bend region and tends to zero as r_0 approaches infinity. However, equation (12) indicates that the shear rate is not constant across the thickness of the sheet. The maximum shear rate occurs at the inside radius of the bend and the minimum shear

rate occurs at the outside radius. As the roller radius increases and the sheet thickness decreases these rates tend towards the same value. The average shear rate is defined by

$$\dot{\phi}_{avg} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} \dot{\phi} dr = \frac{1}{h} \int_{r_0}^{r_0+h} \frac{V}{r} dr = \frac{V}{h} \ln \left(1 + \frac{h}{r_0} \right) \quad (14)$$

Using the equilibrium equation (9) it is a straightforward matter to determine the fibre tension

$$T^* = \int_0^{\phi} S^* d\phi = \frac{m_L V^n}{1-n} \left[\frac{1}{(r_0+h)^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{r_0^{n-1}} \right] \phi + T_0^* \quad (15)$$

As there is no back tension in region ABGH in Figure 2, $T_0^*=0$ and the tension in the fibres increases linearly with ϕ . The fibre tension reaches its maximum value, T_{max}^* , when $\phi=\phi_0$. Lastly we consider the pressure on the large roller as a result of the shearing action. Within the fan region BCFG the shear stress is independent of ϕ , so the second equation in (9) yields

$$p_0 = \frac{T^*}{r_0} = \frac{m_L V^n}{r_0(1-n)} \left[\frac{1}{(r_0+h)^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{r_0^{n-1}} \right] \phi \quad (16)$$

Thus the hydrostatic pressure within the sheet is a maximum at the inside radius and decreases to zero at the outside radius of the bend. In addition to the distributed load on the inside radius of the sheet, two reaction forces must be applied to the strip to keep it in contact with the large roller in Figure 2. Because statically admissible solutions for incompressible inextensible materials admit stress discontinuities, a positive radial force must be applied at point B and a negative radial force must be applied at point F equal to the jump in shear stress across the n -lines BG and CF respectively. These finite point loads and the distributed pressure, p_0 , cause the strip to spread normal to the plane, when there are no side constraints in the bend region. From the foregoing analysis it is clear that additional bends generate extra tension in the fibres in a commutative manner. In this particular study the roller bend apparatus causes the strip to deform into four fan regions of equal angle, ϕ_0 . Hence, the total load, P , to pull the laminate through the four bends is

$$P = 4wT_{max}^* = 4w \frac{m_L V^n}{r_0(1-n)} \left[\frac{1}{(r_0+h)^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{r_0^{n-1}} \right] \phi_0 \quad (17)$$

where w is the width of the sheet. As the fibre tension increases, the hydrostatic pressure in the sheet also increases. In the special case when $n=1$, equations (13) and (15)-(17) become invalid. The fibre tension, the hydrostatic pressure and the drawing loads become linear functions of the forming speed and the hyperbolic term with respect to the radius is replaced by the natural log term in equation (14).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The test specimens were prepared using PLYTRON pre-preg uni-directional plies. PLYTRON is a PP/GF material supplied by Borealis Ltd. with a 35% fibre volume fraction

and a melting temperature of 168°C. The pre-preg plies were consolidated between heated platens in a Satim press at a pressure of 1MPa to produce a 9.3mm thick laminate. This laminate was subsequently cut up into test strips 340mm long and 9.3mm wide. The experimental apparatus consisted of four sets of rolls supported between two parallel plates as shown in Figure 4. The parallel plates were attached to a base plate which was screwed onto a cylindrical Aluminium tube. An additional carbon/epoxy tube was subsequently attached to this tube. Each set of rolls consisted of a large roll and a small roll. These were designed so that the test specimens could fit into a 10mm square gap, as shown in Figure 5. This gap was slightly larger than the dimensions of the test specimens to allow for thermal expansion in the polymer upon melting. By inserting the strips in the roller bend apparatus at 0° or 90°, the inter-ply and the intra-ply shear properties could be measured respectively. The upper three sets of rolls could be located in three different positions to test bend angles of 41.4°, 60° and 90°. After some initial tests the 41.4° bend angle was selected to minimise the hydrostatic pressure in the strip during forming. The roller bearing system consisted of tapered stainless steel pins, which were spring loaded to apply a constant side force to the rollers. This arrangement was cost effective and eliminated the need for high temperature ball bearings. The bulk of the test equipment, including the rolls, was manufactured from Aluminium to minimise the thermal capacity of the device. The test equipment was mounted in an environmental chamber and attached to the cross-head of a Zwick tensile testing machine. The oven and the apparatus were pre-heated to the melting temperature of the specimen. To eliminate any thermal gradients in the chamber, the carbon/epoxy cylindrical tube was used to insulate the apparatus from the ambient temperature outside the oven. Each test strip was gripped by a set of spring loaded jaws inside the oven and allowed to hang in the environmental chamber between the rolls. The forming rolls were initially aligned with the specimen to avoid bending it until it had reached its melting temperature. A thermocouple was put into each sheet at a point 50mm below the grips, to ensure an accurate measurement of the strip temperature. As soon as the matrix polymer had completely melted, the forming rolls were translated in the horizontal direction and fixed in place. A further 15 minutes was then allowed to let the strip temperature stabilise. The Zwick cross-head was moved downwards, so that the strip was pulled through the roller bend apparatus at speeds of 100-1000 mm/min. While the strips were being formed, a 1kN load cell was used to measure the drawing loads. The load data was stored on disk and the results are illustrated in the next section.

Fig. 4: A plan view of the rolls

Fig. 5: Experimental apparatus

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first set of experimental results, shown in Figure 6, illustrates the effect of forming speed on the inter-ply shear response of PLYTRON at 180°C. The first thing which is immediately evident from these results is the small forces needed to draw the thermoplastic composite specimens through the bending rolls. Secondly, the curves follow a consistent pattern and demonstrate some fluctuations in the steady state region. These fluctuations become more irregular with increasing forming speed. For a viscous fluid material it is not surprising that the drawing loads increase with the forming speed; however, the drawing speed has increased by an order of magnitude, while the steady state drawing forces have only increased by a factor of three. This result demonstrates the non-Newtonian shear thinning behaviour of PLYTRON. To eliminate the transient start up phase and the unsteady tail end results, the average steady state forming load was calculated for displacements from 30mm to 80mm. These average values are indicated by dotted lines in Figure 6. The effect of forming speed on the intra-ply drawing forces is demonstrated in Figure 7. Again the forming loads increase non-linearly with the forming speed. In this case the shape of the load curves is similar to those shown in Figure 6 except at higher forming speeds, where the curves tend to rise to a peak and then drop down to a much lower value for the remainder of the process. This feature may be explained in terms of the transverse spreading phenomenon, which was caused by the hydrostatic pressure in the bend region. Unfortunately the experimental side plates could not extend to the outside thickness of the bend because of physical interference from the other rolls. So instead of deforming in a plane strain mode, the edges of the strip tended to widen in the regions between the rolls and then get squashed at the points where the rolls came into contact with each other. This was particularly a problem for the intra-ply specimens at higher forming speeds and is evident by the increasing irregularity in the load results of Figure 7. This problem could be solved by introducing fixed side plates over the entire lengths of the

Figure 6: Drawing load versus displacement for inter-ply shear tests at various forming speeds. Forming temperature=180°C

Figure 7: Drawing load versus displacement for Intra-ply shear tests at various forming speeds. Forming temperature=180°C

strips. Such a physical constraint would add a friction load to the side of the specimens, but this could be measured and subtracted from the total load to determine the fibre tension due to shearing. Alternatively, interlocking sprockets could be used instead of solid circular side plates.

Figure 8: A log-log plot of the steady state loads versus forming speed

At each forming speed a dead load test was performed to determine the friction load associated with the roller bearings and polymer adhesion. By pulling a straight strip through the aligned rolls, the steady state dead load was found to be 0.3N regardless of the forming speed. This dead load was subtracted from the average gross forming loads shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. Using this data, the drawing forces were plotted against the forming speed on a log-log scale and a linear regression was used to determine the pseudo longitudinal shear viscosity and the consistency index of the material from equation (17). The linear regression curves and the experimental steady state forming loads are shown in Figure 8. For the intra-ply tests the 1000mm/min data point was ignored in the regression analysis due to the unreliability caused by the transverse spreading effects.

The results indicate that the intra-ply shear viscosity of PLYTRON is about 25% higher than the inter-ply shear viscosity. Given the possible error in the intra-ply drawing loads at higher forming speeds, it is likely that the consistency indices could be much closer to each other in reality. A typical n value for Polypropylene is 0.3-0.4. Thus the shear thinning effect is most likely attributed to the behaviour of the polymer and is only mildly affected by the presence of the fibres. In comparison with the vee-bend test results [10] for the inter-ply shear viscosity of PLYTRON, the roller bend inter-ply shear viscosity appears to be about 75 times greater. This massive increase in the shear viscosity may be due to the present use of a thin pre-preg material. This unexpected outcome might be explained by considering the micro-structure in the experimental specimens. Micrographs of the specimens used in the roller bend tests, with an average ply thickness of 0.2125mm, showed a much more uniform fibre distribution in comparison with the specimens used for the vee-bend tests. In particular, the vee bend test specimens were made from 0.5mm thick plies and showed resin rich regions between the plies and bundled fibre spacing within the laminate. The vee-bend specimens would probably show a significant difference between their inter-ply and intra-ply shear properties. For a homogeneous micro-structure the inter-ply and intra-ply shear viscosities converge. Thus the composite tends towards a transversely isotropic material behaviour. The increased shear viscosity in the current results has implications regarding the formability of the material. A

CFRT material which resists shear deformation will naturally require higher forming stresses and is more likely to exhibit fibre wrinkling and gross buckling. In the current experimental setup the elastic loads are applied directly to the rollers, while the load cell only measures the viscous energy dissipated by the movement of the strip. If the material exhibits visco-elastic effects, these can only be considered by measuring the loads on the rolls. This feature could be incorporated into future tests.

CONCLUSIONS

The *roller bend technique* is in principle ideally suited to isolating and measuring the inter-ply and intra-ply shear properties of molten continuous fibre thermoplastic composites. The experimental method can be easily executed and the steady state drawing forces can be quickly converted into steady shear viscosity data. The theory also correctly predicts the transverse spreading of the uni-directional laminates due to shearing. Unfortunately, the multi-bend apparatus did not enforce a plane strain condition across the entire strip thickness, so the test specimens attempted to spread rather than shear during forming. More reliable experimental data might be obtained with fixed side plates or interlocking sprocket side plates. A comparison between the inter-ply and intra-ply shear properties of PLYTRON was made possible using the *roller bend technique*. This has never been done before. The results indicate that for a homogeneously distributed fibre micro-structure, the intra-ply viscosity is not much greater than the inter-ply viscosity. Consequently, the material behaves in a nearly transversely isotropic manner. The reduction in viscosity of the composite with increasing forming speed appears to be independent of the in-plane or out-of-plane shear mode and can be attributed to the power-law shear thinning behaviour of the polymer matrix. The calculated inter-ply pseudo longitudinal viscosity of PLYTRON was found to be significantly higher than that reported elsewhere. This could be due to the use of a thinner pre-preg material and a uniform distribution of fibres across the laminate. Further experimental investigation is required to verify this finding.

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